

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING INNOVATIVE METHODS IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *The article deals with the tasks of a modern school, the manifestation of creative abilities, the introduction of the variability of educational processes, where there are various innovative types and types of educational institutions that require comprehensive scientific and practical views.*

Keywords: *comprehensive, scientific, practical views.*

According to the development of modern information society requirements for its participants, are getting higher every year. These requirements apply not only to the high level of geopolitical economic requirements imposed on modern worker, but also a comprehensive training and development of an individual to participate in all spheres of social and political life. Thus, the need for foreign language learning becomes a fashionable trend or additional educational baggage of the person, but an

objective reality and the introduction of innovative educational technologies for fast and efficient learning a foreign language is the key to the need for every citizen of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Currently in our country there are significant changes in the national education policy. This is due to the transition to the position of student centered pedagogy. One of the tasks of modern school becomes a potential disclosure of all participants in the pedagogical process, providing them with opportunities manifestation of creative abilities. Solving these problems is impossible without the implementation of the variability of educational processes, in connection with which there are various innovative types and kinds of educational institutions, which require in-depth scientific and practical thinking. Modern school is the result of the huge changes that have occurred in the system of Russian education in recent years. In this sense, education is not just a part of social life, and its avant-garde: hardly any other subsystem it to the same extent can confirm the fact of the progressive development of such an abundance of innovations and experiments [1]. Today, many are looking for ways that would help improve the effectiveness of training. Teachers always excites the actual

problem is to make sure that all the students were interested in a lesson to all involved in the learning process, so that there are no indifferent. How to use stories to develop the personality of the student, his creative thinking, the ability to analyze the past and present, to make their own conclusions and to have their own point of view? All these tasks can be implemented under conditions of vigorous activity of students using interactive methods and teacher training methods. Therein lies the essence of teaching. Thus, the main objective of educational activities is the development of students' abilities to integrated thinking that will help them to see new aspects of the phenomenon, it creates a holistic vision of the world and, therefore, easier to find your place in it. To accomplish this goal it is necessary to solve the following tasks: - To examine and summarize the best practices of the problem with the use of the lessons active and interactive methods; - Describe the technology of application of interactive teaching methods to improve the quality of education and to help students fulfill cognitive creativity; - To identify whether all the necessary components and tools are available for the implementation of this technology - To orient students to the perception and the collective decision of complex issues on the basis of the maximum mental stress; - To teach students to apply their knowledge in practice. Combining traditional with interactive lessons allow to achieve the best results and to fulfill the goals and objectives, that is, will "look and try on the ways of learning that students will be happy." At present, priority is given to communicative, interactive, authentic communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy and humanization of education. These principles make possible the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative ability.

The ultimate goal of foreign language teaching is learning to free orientation in a foreign environment and the ability to adequately respond in different situations, ie, communication. Today, new methods of using the Internet - resources are opposed to the traditional teaching of foreign languages. To learn to communicate in a foreign language, you need to create a real, real life situation (ie, what is called the principle of the authenticity of the communication), which will stimulate the study of the material and generate adequate behavior. This error trying to fix the new technologies, particularly the Internet [2]. In recent years, increasingly it raises the question of the application of innovative technology in the classroom. It is not only new facilities but also new forms and methods of teaching, new approach to learning.

Introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process is interconnected with the improvement of the content and methods of education in the process of teaching foreign languages in relation to the needs of modern life.

The main objective of foreign language teaching is the formation and development of the communicative culture of pupils, learning practical mastery of a foreign language.

The task of the teacher is to create the conditions of practical language learning for each student to choose such training methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity. Modern teaching techniques such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to realize the learner - centered approach to learning, providing personalization and differentiation of learning abilities of children, taking into account their level of training. The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates the communication, aimed at creating a psychological and linguistic readiness to communicate, on a conscious understanding of the material and methods of action with him. For the user, the implementation of the communicative approach in the Internet is not particularly difficult.

Communicative job must offer students a problem or question for discussion, and students do not just share information, but also evaluate it. But the main criterion to distinguish this approach from other types of learning activities is that students choose their own linguistic units to process their thoughts. Using the Internet in the communicative approach could not be better motivated: its aim is to interest students in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of their knowledge and experience. One of the basic requirements for teaching foreign languages using the Internet - resources, is to create interaction in the classroom, what is called in interactive methods. Interactivity is a "unification, coordination and complementarity of efforts communicative purpose and outcome of speech means."

Teaching genuine language, the Internet helps in shaping the conversation, as well as in teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing a genuine interest and, hence, efficiency. Interactivity is not just creating real situations of life, but also makes the students to adequately respond to them through a foreign language [3]. One of the technologies, providing personality - oriented training is a method of projects as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of the projects varied, projects can be divided into monoprotected, collective, oral, specific, written and Internet - projects. Although in actual practice often have to deal with mixed project in which there is evidence of research, creativity, practice - oriented and information.

Work on the project - a multilevel approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. Project based learning promotes active independent thinking of students and orients them on a joint research work. In my

opinion, project learning true that teaches children cooperation and training problem or question for discussion, and students do not just share information, but also evaluate it. But the main criterion to distinguish this approach from other types of learning activities is that students choose their own linguistic units to process their thoughts. Using the Internet in the communicative approach could not be better motivated: its aim is to interest students in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of their knowledge and experience. One of the basic requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources, is to create interaction in the classroom, what is called in interactive methods. Interactivity is a "unification, coordination and complementarity of efforts communicative purpose and outcome of speech means." Teaching genuine language, the Internet helps in shaping the conversation, as well as in teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing a genuine interest and, hence, efficiency. Interactivity is not just creating real situations of life, but also makes the students to adequately respond to them through a foreign language [2]. One of the technologies that provides student-centered learning, is a method of projects as a Project-based forms of students communication skills, communication, culture, skills, concise and accessible to formulate thoughts, to tolerate the opinion of the partners in dialogue, to develop the ability to extract information from different sources, process it with the help of modern computer technology, creates a language environment conducive to the emergence of the natural needs in communicating in a foreign language. The project form of work is one of the important technologies that allow students to apply the acquired knowledge on the subject. Students broaden their horizons, the boundaries of language proficiency, gaining experience from its practical use, study foreign language listen to it and hear, to understand each other in the protection project.

Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computer, thus creates the possibility of direct contact with authentic language, which does not give learning a language only using the textbook in the classroom in the classroom. Work on the project is a creative process. The student independently or under the supervision of the teacher is looking for solutions to some problems, this requires not only knowledge of the language but also the possession of a large volume of subject knowledge, knowledge of creative, communicative and intellectual skills. The foreign language course project method can be used in the framework of the program material on virtually any topic. Work on the project develops the imagination, imagination, creative thinking, self-reliance and other personal qualities [5]. The use of innovative teaching methods in the classroom of a foreign language can greatly improve the speech skills of the student and the student

interest in the subject.

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